

REVISITING YANO AND ZYGMUND EXTRAPOLATION THEORY

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ABSTRACT. We prove a pointwise estimate for the decreasing rearrangement of Tf , where T is any sublinear operator satisfying the weak-type boundedness

$$T : L^{p_0,1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p_1,\infty}(\nu), \quad \forall p : 1 < p_0 < p \leq p_1 < \infty,$$

with norm controlled by $C\varphi\left([p_0^{-1} - p^{-1}]^{-1}\right)$ and φ satisfies some admissibility conditions. The pointwise estimate is:

$$(Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim \frac{1}{p_0 - 1} \left(\frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi\left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t}\right) f_\mu^*(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^\infty f_\mu^*(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}} \right).$$

In particular, this estimate allows to obtain extensions of Yano and Zygmund extrapolation results.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1951, Yano (see [10, 11]) using the ideas of Titchmarsh in [9], proved that for every sublinear operator T satisfying that, for some $\alpha > 0$ and for every $1 < p \leq p_1$,

$$T : L^p(\mu) \longrightarrow L^p(\nu), \quad \frac{C}{(p-1)^\alpha},$$

where (\mathcal{M}, μ) and (\mathcal{N}, ν) are two finite measure spaces, it holds that

$$T : L(\log L)^\alpha(\mu) \longrightarrow L^1(\nu),$$

where the space $L(\log L)^\alpha(\mu)$ is defined as the set of μ -measurable functions such that

$$\|f\|_{L(\log L)^\alpha(\mu)} = \int_0^\infty f_\mu^*(t) \left(1 + \log^+ \frac{1}{t}\right)^\alpha dt < \infty,$$

where $a^+ = \max(a, 0)$, for every $a \in \mathbb{R}$, f_μ^* is the decreasing rearrangement of f with respect to the measure μ defined as

$$f_\mu^*(t) = \inf \left\{ y > 0 : \lambda_f^\mu(y) \leq t \right\}, \quad t > 0,$$

and

$$\lambda_f^\mu(y) = \mu(\{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : |f(x)| > y\}), \quad y > 0,$$

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is the distribution function of f with respect to μ . (Here we are using the standard notation $\mu(E) = \int_E d\mu(x)$ for every μ -measurable set $E \subseteq X$. If $d\mu = dx$, we shall write f^* , $\lambda_f(y)$ and $|E|$. See [4] for more details about this topic).

If the measures involved are not finite, it was proved in [5] and [6] that under a weaker condition on the operator T , namely

$$\left(\int_{\mathcal{N}} |T\chi_A(x)|^p d\nu(x) \right)^{1/p} \leq \frac{C}{p-1} \mu(A)^{1/p},$$

for every μ -measurable set $A \subset \mathcal{M}$ and every $1 < p \leq p_0$, with C independent of A and p , then

$$T : L(\log L)^\alpha(\mu) \longrightarrow M(\phi),$$

where $M(\phi)$ is the maximal Lorentz space associated to the function $\phi(t) = \frac{t}{1+\log^+ t}$, $t > 0$; that is,

$$\|f\|_{M(\phi)} = \sup_{t>0} \phi(t) f_\nu^{**}(t) = \sup_{t>1} \frac{t f_\nu^{**}(t)}{1 + \log t},$$

where $f_\nu^{**}(t) = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t f_\nu^*(s) ds$, $t > 0$. These results belong to what is known as Yano's extrapolation theory.

On the other hand, in [11, p. 119] it was seen that if T is a linear operator satisfying

$$(1.1) \quad \|Tf\|_{L^p(\nu)} \leq Cp \|f\|_{L^p(\mu)},$$

for every p near ∞ and for μ and ν being finite measures, then

$$T : L^\infty(\mu) \longrightarrow L_{\text{exp}}(\nu),$$

where $L_{\text{exp}}(\nu)$ is the set of ν -measurable functions satisfying that

$$\|f\|_{L_{\text{exp}}(\nu)} = \sup_{0 < t < 1} \frac{f_\nu^{**}(t)}{1 + \log \frac{1}{t}},$$

and this result was also extended to the case of general measures (see [6]) proving that, if T is a linear operator satisfying (1.1), then

$$(1.2) \quad \sup_{0 < t < 1} \frac{(Tf)_\nu^{**}(t)}{1 + \log \frac{1}{t}} \lesssim \|f\|_{L^\infty(\mu)} + \int_1^\infty f_\mu^{**}(s) \frac{ds}{s},$$

where, as usual, we write $A \lesssim B$ if there exists a positive constant $C > 0$, independent of A and B , such that $A \leq CB$. If $A \lesssim B$ and $B \lesssim A$, then we write $A \approx B$. These results belong to what is known as Zygmund's extrapolation theory.

For the purpose of this work, it is also interesting to mention that analogue results are known to the ones commented above in the case that, for some $1 < p_0 < p_1 < \infty$ and every $p_0 < p < p_1$,

$$T : L^p(\mu) \longrightarrow L^p(\nu)$$

with

$$\|T\|_{L^p(\mu) \rightarrow L^p(\nu)} \lesssim \frac{1}{(p-p_0)^\alpha} \quad \text{or} \quad \|T\|_{L^p(\mu) \rightarrow L^p(\nu)} \lesssim \frac{1}{(p_1-p)^\alpha}, \quad \alpha > 0.$$

The exact statements are the following:

Theorem 1.1. ([7]) *Let T be a sublinear operator satisfying that for every $p_0 < p \leq p_1$,*

$$T : L^p(\mu) \longrightarrow L^p(\nu), \quad \frac{C}{p - p_0}.$$

Then,

$$\sup_{t>1} \frac{\left(\int_0^t (Tf)_\nu^*(s)^{p_0} ds \right)^{1/p_0}}{1 + \log t} \lesssim \|f\|_{L^{p_0}(\mu)} + \int_0^1 \frac{\left(\int_0^r f_\mu^*(s)^{p_0} ds \right)^{1/p_0}}{r} dr.$$

Theorem 1.2. ([7]) *Let T be a sublinear operator satisfying that for every $p_0 \leq p < p_1$,*

$$T : L^p(\mu) \longrightarrow L^p(\nu), \quad \frac{C}{p_1 - p}.$$

Then,

$$\sup_{0<t<1} \frac{\left(\int_t^\infty (Tf)_\nu^*(s)^{p_1} ds \right)^{1/p_1}}{1 + \log \frac{1}{t}} \lesssim \|f\|_{L^{p_1}(\mu)} + \int_1^\infty \frac{\left(\int_r^\infty f_\mu^*(s)^{p_1} ds \right)^{1/p_1}}{r} dr.$$

There is also a Yano's extrapolation theorem concerning weak-type spaces. In 1996, N.Yu. Antonov [2] proved that there is almost everywhere convergence for the Fourier series of every function in $L \log L \log_3 L(\mathbb{T})$, where \mathbb{T} represents the unit circle and, for an arbitrary measure μ ,

$$\|f\|_{L \log L \log_3 L(\mu)} = \int_0^\infty f_\mu^*(t) \log_1 \frac{1}{t} \log_3 \frac{1}{t} dt < \infty,$$

with

$$(1.3) \quad \log_1 t = 1 + \log^+ t \quad \text{and} \quad \log_k t = \log_1 \log_{k-1} t \quad \text{for } k > 1, \quad t > 0.$$

Indeed, even though he did not write it explicitly, behind his ideas there is an extrapolation argument (see [3, 5] for more details). Before we make its statement precise, let us recall that, given $1 \leq p < \infty$ and $0 < q < \infty$, the Lorentz spaces $L^{p,q}(\mu)$ are defined as the set of μ -measurable functions f such that

$$\|f\|_{L^{p,q}(\mu)} = \left(\int_0^\infty t^{\frac{q}{p}-1} f_\mu^*(t)^q dt \right)^{1/q} = \left(p \int_0^\infty t^{q-1} \lambda_f^\mu(y)^{\frac{q}{p}} dy \right)^{1/q} < \infty,$$

and

$$\|f\|_{L^{p,\infty}(\mu)} = \sup_{t>0} t^{\frac{1}{p}} f_\mu^*(t) = \sup_{y>0} y \lambda_f^\mu(y)^{\frac{1}{p}} < \infty.$$

Theorem 1.3. *If T is a sublinear operator such that for some $\alpha > 0$ and for every $1 < p \leq p_0$,*

$$T : L^{p,1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(\nu), \quad \frac{C}{(p-1)^\alpha},$$

then

$$T : L(\log L)^\alpha \log_3 L(\mu) \rightarrow L^{1,\infty}(\nu).$$

Since all the spaces above mentioned are rearrangement invariant, all the results could be also obtained if we find a good estimate for the function $(Tf)^*$ and, moreover, in this case, we can deduce boundedness of T in other rearrangement invariant spaces as well. At this point, we should recall the following well-known pointwise estimate:

Theorem 1.4. ([4, Ch. 4.4 Theorem 4.11]) *Let $1 \leq p_0 < p_1 < \infty$. A sublinear operator T satisfies that*

$$T : L^{p_0,1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p_0,\infty}(\nu) \quad \text{and} \quad T : L^{p_1,1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p_1,\infty}(\nu),$$

if and only if, for every $t > 0$ and every μ -measurable function f ,

$$(Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim \frac{1}{t^{p_0}} \int_0^t f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \frac{1}{t^{p_1}} \int_t^\infty f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}}.$$

Moreover, with the goal of finding interesting pointwise estimates for the function $(Tf)^*$ under weaker conditions on T , the following results have been recently proved in [1] (see Definition 2.1 for the notion of admissible function):

Theorem 1.5. *Let T be a sublinear operator and φ some admissible function. For every $1 \leq p < \infty$,*

$$T : L^{p,1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(\nu), \quad C\varphi(p),$$

if and only if, for every $t > 0$ and every μ -measurable function f ,

$$(Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t f_\mu^*(s) ds + \int_t^\infty \left(1 + \log \frac{s}{t}\right)^{-1} \varphi\left(1 + \log \frac{s}{t}\right) f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s}.$$

We observe that, if $\varphi(p) = p$ (which is an admissible function),

$$(Tf)_\nu^{**}(t) \lesssim \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t f_\mu^{**}(s) ds + \int_t^\infty f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s}$$

and hence

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{0 < t < 1} \frac{(Tf)_\nu^{**}(t)}{1 + \log \frac{1}{t}} &\lesssim \|f\|_\infty + \int_1^\infty f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s} + \sup_{0 < t < 1} \frac{1}{1 + \log \frac{1}{t}} \int_t^1 f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s} \\ &\lesssim \|f\|_\infty + \int_1^\infty f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s}, \end{aligned}$$

and we recover (1.2).

We have to mention here that although we have obtained a better estimate, we have, initially, assumed a stronger condition, since our boundedness hypothesis also includes the case $p = 1$. However, if the boundedness information is only for $p \geq p_0 > 1$, we also have the following result (see [1]) from which (1.2) can also be recovered:

Theorem 1.6. *Take $1 \leq p_0 < p_1 \leq \infty$ and let T be a sublinear operator and φ some admissible function. Assume that for every $p_0 \leq p < p_1$,*

$$T : L^{p,1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(\nu), \quad C\varphi\left(\left[\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p_1}\right]^{-1}\right).$$

Then, for every $t > 0$ and every μ -measurable function f :

(i) If $p_1 < \infty$,

$$(1.4) \quad (Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^\infty \varphi \left(1 + \log \frac{s}{t} \right) f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}}.$$

(ii) If $p_1 = \infty$,

$$(1.5) \quad (Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \int_t^\infty \left(1 + \log \frac{s}{t} \right)^{-1} \varphi \left(1 + \log \frac{s}{t} \right) f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s}.$$

Conversely, if (1.4) holds then, for every $p_0 \leq p < p_1$,

$$\|T\|_{L^{p,1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(\nu)} \lesssim \left[\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p_1} \right]^{-1} \varphi \left(\left[\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{p_1} \right]^{-1} \right),$$

while if (1.5) holds, $\|T\|_{L^{p,1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p,\infty}(\nu)} \lesssim \varphi(p)$.

Our goal in this note is to prove similar results to those in Theorems 1.5 and 1.6, to obtain extensions of Yano's extrapolation results. Moreover, we want to emphasize here, that we obtain stronger results with a simpler proof because contrary to what happens in the proof of the above mentioned results of Yano and Zygmund, where the function f is decomposed in an infinite sum of functions f_n , our proof follows the idea of Theorem 1.4 where the function f is decomposed as the sum of just two functions.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we present previous results, the necessary definitions and some technical lemmas which shall be used later on, and Section 3 contains our main results.

2. DEFINITIONS, PREVIOUS RESULTS AND LEMMAS

2.1. Admissible functions.

Definition 2.1 ([1]). A function $\varphi : [1, \infty) \rightarrow [1, \infty)$ is said to be *admissible* if satisfies the following conditions:

a) $\varphi(1) = 1$ and φ is log-concave, that is

$$\theta \log \varphi(x) + (1 - \theta) \log \varphi(y) \leq \log \varphi(\theta x + (1 - \theta)y), \quad \forall x, y \geq 1, \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq 1.$$

b) There exist $\gamma, \beta > 0$ such that for every $x \geq 1$,

$$(2.1) \quad \frac{\gamma}{x} \leq \frac{\varphi'(x)}{\varphi(x)} \leq \frac{\beta}{x}.$$

Observe that (2.1) implies that φ is increasing, as well as that

$$x^\gamma \leq \varphi(x) \leq x^\beta.$$

Besides, since for every $x, y \geq 1$,

$$\log \varphi(xy) = \int_1^y (\log \varphi)'(s) ds + \int_y^{xy} (\log \varphi)'(s) ds \leq \log \varphi(y) + \beta \log x,$$

it also holds that

$$(2.2) \quad \varphi(xy) \leq x^\beta \varphi(y).$$

Example 2.2. Given $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and using the notation in (1.3), if $\gamma > 0$ and $\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m \geq 0$, the function

$$\varphi(x) = x^\gamma \prod_{k=1}^m (\log_k x)^{\beta_k}, \quad x \geq 1,$$

is admissible.

The next lemma is a simple computation for admissible functions which shall be fundamental in the proof of our main results.

Lemma 2.3. *Let φ be an admissible function. For $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $1 \leq q_0 < \infty$,*

$$\inf_{q \in [q_0, \infty)} \varphi(q) e^{-\frac{x}{q}} \leq \begin{cases} \varphi(q_0) e^{-\frac{x}{q_0}}, & \text{if } x \geq 0, \\ q_0^\beta e^{\frac{1}{q_0}} \varphi(1-x), & \text{if } x < 0. \end{cases}$$

Proof. If $x \geq 0$, the infimum is attained at $q = q_0$, and if $x < 0$, we take $q = q_0(1-x)$ and make use of (2.2). \square

2.2. Calderón type operators.

Definition 2.4. Let $1 \leq p_0, p_1 \leq \infty$ and let φ be an admissible function. Then, for every positive and real valued measurable function f and $t > 0$, we define

$$P_{p_0, \varphi} f(t) := \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi\left(1 - \log \frac{s}{t}\right) f(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}},$$

$$Q_{p_1} f(t) := \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^\infty f(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}},$$

and

$$R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi} f(t) := P_{p_0, \varphi} f(t) + Q_{p_1} f(t).$$

In particular, if $p_0 = 1$, $p_1 = \infty$, and $\varphi(x) = 1$, we recover the Calderón operator [4]

$$Rf(t) := Pf(t) + Qf(t), \quad t > 0,$$

where P and Q are respectively the Hardy operator and its conjugate

$$Pf(t) = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t f(s) ds, \quad Qf(t) = \int_t^\infty f(s) \frac{ds}{s}, \quad t > 0.$$

We observe that, in general,

$$(2.3) \quad R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi} f(t) = \int_0^1 \varphi(1 - \log s) f(st) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \int_1^\infty f(st) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}}, \quad t > 0.$$

Lemma 2.5. *Let $1 \leq p_0, p_1 \leq \infty$. For an arbitrary measure μ and every μ -measurable function f ,*

$$R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi} (f_\mu^*)^{**}(t) = R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi} (f_\mu^{**})(t), \quad t > 0.$$

Proof. By (2.3), clearly, $R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi} (f_\mu^*)$ is a decreasing function. Then, it holds that

$$R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi} (f_\mu^*)^{**}(t) = P(R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi} (f_\mu^*))(t), \quad t > 0,$$

and the result follows immediately by the Fubini's theorem. \square

3. MAIN RESULTS

Throughout this section, if not specified, (\mathcal{M}, μ) and (\mathcal{N}, ν) are two arbitrary measure spaces.

Theorem 3.1. *Take $1 < p_0 < p_1 < \infty$ and let T be a sublinear operator and φ some admissible function. If for every $p_0 < p \leq p_1$,*

$$(3.1) \quad T : L^{p,1}(\mu) \longrightarrow L^{p,\infty}(\nu), \quad C\varphi \left(\left[\frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p} \right]^{-1} \right),$$

then, for every $t > 0$ and every μ -measurable function f ,

$$(3.2) \quad \begin{aligned} (Tf)_\nu^*(t) &\lesssim \frac{1}{p_0 - 1} \left(\frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t} \right) f_\mu^*(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^\infty f_\mu^*(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{p_0 - 1} R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t). \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, if $(Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t)$ for every $t > 0$, then, for each $p_0 < p \leq p_1$, (3.1) holds.

Proof. First assume that (3.1) applies for every $p_0 < p \leq p_1$. Then, if $f = \chi_E$ for some μ -measurable set $E \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $\mu(E) < \infty$, for every $t > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t) &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t} \right) \chi_{(0, \mu(E))}(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^\infty \chi_{(0, \mu(E))}(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^{\mu(E)} \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}} \right) \chi_{(0, \mu(E))}(t) \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^{\mu(E)} \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} \right) \chi_{(\mu(E), \infty)}(t) \\ &\geq p_0 \left[\left(\frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p_1}} \chi_{(0, \mu(E))}(t) + \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right) \left(\frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \chi_{(\mu(E), \infty)}(t) \right], \end{aligned}$$

where in the last estimate we have used that $p_1 > p_0$, $\varphi(1) = 1$ and that $\varphi(1 - \log \frac{s}{t})$ is a decreasing function on $s \in (0, t)$.

Hence, since by hypothesis, for every $p_0 < p \leq p_1$ we have that

$$(T\chi_E)_\nu^*(t) \leq C\varphi \left(\left[\frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p} \right]^{-1} \right) \left(\frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = C \left[\varphi(q) \left(\frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right)^{-\frac{1}{q}} \right] \left(\frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p_0}}, \quad t > 0,$$

with $\frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p}$, the result for characteristic functions plainly follows by taking the infimum for $q \in \left[\frac{p_1 p_0}{p_1 - p_0}, \infty \right)$ (see Lemma 2.3) since then, for every $t > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} (T\chi_E)_\nu^*(t) &\lesssim \left(\frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p_1}} \chi_{(0, \mu(E))}(t) + \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right) \left(\frac{\mu(E)}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \chi_{(\mu(E), \infty)}(t) \\ &\lesssim R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}((\chi_E)_\mu^*)(t). \end{aligned}$$

The extension to simple functions with sets of finite measure with respect to μ follows the same lines as the proof of Theorem III.4.7 of [4]. We include the computations adapted to our case for the convenience of the reader. First of all, consider a positive simple function

$$f = \sum_{j=1}^n a_j \chi_{F_j},$$

where $F_1 \subseteq F_2 \subseteq \dots \subseteq F_n$ have finite measure with respect to μ . Then

$$f_\mu^* = \sum_{j=1}^n a_j \chi_{[0, \mu(F_j))}.$$

Using what we have already proved for characteristic functions we get that for every $t > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} (Tf)_\nu^{**}(t) &\lesssim \sum_{j=1}^n a_j (T(\chi_{F_j}))_\nu^{**}(t) \lesssim \sum_{j=1}^n a_j (R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(\chi_{[0, \mu(F_j))}))^{**}(t) \\ &= \left(R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n a_j \chi_{[0, \mu(F_j))} \right) \right)^{**}(t) = R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)^{**}(t). \end{aligned}$$

Further, since $R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)^{**} = R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^{**})$ (see Lemma 2.5) we obtain that

$$(3.3) \quad (Tf)_\nu^{**}(t) \lesssim R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^{**})(t), \quad t > 0.$$

Now fix $t > 0$ and consider the set $E = \{x : f(x) > f_\mu^*(t)\}$. Using this set define

$$g = (f - f_\mu^*(t))\chi_E \quad \text{and} \quad h = f_\mu^*(t)\chi_E + f\chi_{E^c},$$

so that $f = g + h$ and

$$g_\mu^*(s) = (f_\mu^*(s) - f_\mu^*(t))\chi_{(0, t)}(s) \quad \text{and} \quad h_\mu^*(s) = \min\{f_\mu^*(s), f_\mu^*(t)\}, \quad s > 0.$$

Since (3.1) holds with $p = p_1$, the corresponding weak inequality leads to

$$\begin{aligned} (Th)_\nu^*(t/2) &\lesssim \frac{1}{t^{p_1}} \int_0^\infty h_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}} \lesssim f_\mu^*(t) + \frac{1}{t^{p_1}} \int_t^\infty f_\mu^*(s) \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}} \\ &\leq P_{p_0, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t) + Q_{p_1}(f_\mu^*)(t), \end{aligned}$$

where we have used that $f_\mu^*(t) \leq P_{p_0, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t)$.

On the other hand, on account of (3.3) we get

$$(3.4) \quad (Tg)_\nu^{**}(t) \lesssim R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(g_\mu^{**})(t) = P_{p_0, \varphi}(g_\mu^{**})(t) + Q_{p_1}(g_\mu^{**})(t)$$

and for the first term of the right hand side of (3.4) we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{p_0, \varphi}(g_\mu^{**})(t) &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi\left(1 - \log \frac{s}{t}\right) \frac{1}{s} \int_0^s g_\mu^*(r) dr \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} \\
&\leq \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi\left(1 - \log \frac{s}{t}\right) \int_0^s f_\mu^*(r) dr \frac{ds}{s^{2-\frac{1}{p_0}}} \\
(3.5) \quad &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t f_\mu^*(r) \int_r^t \varphi\left(1 - \log \frac{s}{t}\right) \frac{ds}{s^{2-\frac{1}{p_0}}} dr \\
&\leq \frac{p_0}{p_0 - 1} \left(\frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi\left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t}\right) f_\mu^*(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} \right) \\
&= \frac{p_0}{p_0 - 1} P_{p_0, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t),
\end{aligned}$$

while for the second term

$$Q_{p_1}(g_\mu^{**})(t) = \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^\infty \frac{1}{s} \int_0^s g_\mu^*(r) dr \frac{ds}{s^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}} \leq \frac{p_1}{p_1 - 1} f_\mu^{**}(t) \leq \frac{p_0}{p_0 - 1} P_{p_0, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t).$$

Thus,

$$(Tf)_\nu^*(t) \leq 2(Tg)_\nu^{**}(t) + (Th)_\nu^*(t/2) \lesssim \frac{1}{p_0 - 1} R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t),$$

and the general case follows from the density of the simple functions to any μ -measurable function and dividing a μ -measurable function in its positive and negative parts.

Conversely, assume that $(Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t)$ for every $t > 0$ and fix some $p \in (p_0, p_1]$. The operator $R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}$ is a kernel operator; that is

$$R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}f(t) = \int_0^\infty k(t, r)f(r)dr, \quad t > 0,$$

where the kernel is

$$(3.6) \quad k(t, r) = \varphi\left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t}\right) \left(\frac{r}{t}\right)^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \chi_{[0, t)}(r) \frac{1}{r} + \left(\frac{r}{t}\right)^{\frac{1}{p_1}} \chi_{[t, \infty)}(r) \frac{1}{r}.$$

By virtue of [8, Theorem 3.3], the norm $\|R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}\|_{L^{p, 1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p, \infty}}$ can be estimated by

$$A_k := \sup_{t > 0} \left(\sup_{s > 0} \left(\frac{t}{s}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \int_0^s k(t, r)dr \right).$$

Now observe that for $\beta_0 = \max(1, \beta)$ and for every $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, by means of (2.2),

$$\varphi(1 - \log x) \leq \varphi\left(\frac{\beta_0}{\alpha} x^{-\frac{\alpha}{\beta_0}}\right) \leq \varphi\left(\frac{\beta_0}{\alpha}\right) x^{-\frac{\alpha\beta}{\beta_0}} \leq \beta_0^{\beta_0} \varphi\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right) x^{-\alpha}, \quad 0 < x \leq 1.$$

Take $\alpha = \frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p} \in (0, 1)$. Hence, if $0 < s \leq t$,

$$\int_0^s k(t, r) dr = \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^s \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} \leq p_1 \beta_0^{\beta_0} \varphi \left(\left[\frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p} \right]^{-1} \right) \left(\frac{s}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}},$$

while if $s > t$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^s k(t, r) dr &= \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^s \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}} \\ &\leq p_1 \beta_0^{\beta_0} \varphi \left(\left[\frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p} \right]^{-1} \right) + p_1 \left(\frac{s}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

In consequence, we have that

$$A_k \leq p_1 \beta_0^{\beta_0} \varphi \left(\left[\frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p} \right]^{-1} \right) \sup_{t>0} \left(\sup_{s>t} \left(\frac{t}{s} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[1 + \left(\frac{s}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right] \right) = 2p_1 \beta_0^{\beta_0} \varphi \left(\left[\frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p} \right]^{-1} \right). \quad \square$$

Remark 3.2. It is worth mentioning that in order to prove that (3.1) implies (3.2), the only properties that we have used of φ are that φ is a nondecreasing function such that $\varphi(1) = 1$ and that for every constant $C \geq 1$, $\varphi(Cx) \approx \varphi(x)$.

As we mentioned in the introduction, one application of these pointwise estimates is to deduce extensions of Yano's extrapolation results as the following corollary shows. First, for an arbitrary measure μ , some exponent $1 \leq p < \infty$ and some admissible function φ , we define the function space $L^{p,1}\varphi(\log L)(\mu)$ as the set of μ -measurable functions f satisfying

$$\|f\|_{L^{p,1}\varphi(\log L)(\mu)} = \int_0^\infty \varphi \left(1 + \log^+ \frac{1}{r} \right) f_\mu^*(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p}}} < \infty.$$

Corollary 3.3. *Let T be a sublinear operator such that for some $1 < p_0 < p_1 < \infty$ and for every $p_0 < p \leq p_1$,*

$$T : L^{p,1}(\mu) \longrightarrow L^{p,\infty}(\nu), \quad C\varphi \left(\left[\frac{1}{p_0} - \frac{1}{p} \right]^{-1} \right),$$

where φ is an admissible function. Then, if ν is a finite measure,

$$T : L^{p_0,1}\varphi(\log L)(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p_0,\infty}(\nu), \quad \frac{C}{p_0 - 1}.$$

Proof. As a consequence of Theorem 3.1,

$$(Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim \frac{1}{p_0 - 1} R_{p_0,p_1,\varphi}(f_\mu^*)(t), \quad 0 < t < \nu(\mathcal{N}).$$

Further, by means of [8, Theorem 3.3],

$$\|R_{p_0,p_1,\varphi}\|_{L^{p_0,1}\varphi(\log L)(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p_0,\infty}(0,\nu(\mathcal{N}))} \lesssim \sup_{0 < t < \nu(\mathcal{N})} t^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \left[\sup_{s>0} \frac{\int_0^s k(t, r) dr}{\int_0^s \varphi \left(1 + \log^+ \frac{1}{r} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}}} \right],$$

with $k(t, r)$ as in (3.6). Hence, if $0 < s \leq t$,

$$t^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \left[\frac{\int_0^s k(t, r) dr}{\int_0^s \varphi \left(1 + \log^+ \frac{1}{r} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}}} \right] = \frac{\int_0^s \varphi \left(1 + \log \frac{t}{r} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}}}{\int_0^s \varphi \left(1 + \log^+ \frac{1}{r} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}}} \leq \max \left(1, \nu(\mathcal{N})^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \right),$$

while if $s > t$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} t^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \left[\frac{\int_0^s k(t, r) dr}{\int_0^s \varphi \left(1 + \log^+ \frac{1}{r} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}}} \right] &= \frac{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \left(\frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \int_0^t \varphi \left(1 + \log \frac{t}{r} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}} + p_1 \left[\left(\frac{s}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p_1}} - 1 \right] \right)}{\int_0^s \varphi \left(1 + \log^+ \frac{1}{r} \right) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_0}}}} \\ &\leq \frac{t^{\frac{1}{p_0}} \left(C_\varphi + p_1 \left(\frac{s}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{p_1}} \right)}{p_0 s^{\frac{1}{p_0}}} \leq \frac{C_\varphi + p_1}{p_0}, \end{aligned}$$

so that $\|R_{p_0, p_1, \varphi}\|_{L^{p_0, 1} \varphi(\log L)(\mu) \rightarrow L^{p_0, \infty}((0, \nu(\mathcal{N})), dx)} < \infty$. □

Remark 3.4. For $p_0 = 1$, we observe that following the lines of the sufficiency of the proof of Theorem 3.1, the only place where we could have problems is in (3.5), since this estimate blows up as p_0 approximates 1^+ . Nevertheless, easy computations show that then, for every $t > 0$ and every μ -measurable function f ,

$$(Tf)_\nu^*(t) \lesssim \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t \left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t} \right) \varphi \left(1 - \log \frac{r}{t} \right) f_\mu^*(r) dr + \frac{1}{t^{\frac{1}{p_1}}} \int_t^\infty f_\mu^*(r) \frac{dr}{r^{1-\frac{1}{p_1}}}.$$

However, when $\varphi(x) = x^\alpha$, $\alpha > 0$, it can be deduced that for an arbitrary measure μ and a finite measure ν ,

$$T : L(\log L)^{\alpha+1}(\mu) \rightarrow L^{1, \infty}(\nu),$$

which, as we have seen on the introduction, is far from the best results known up to now (see, for instance, Theorem 1.3).

OPEN QUESTION

Can we extend our result to the case $p_0 = 1$ in an optimal way?

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